

**SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL FOR:
HOW TO COMBINE MODELS? PRINCIPLES AND MECHANISMS
TO AGGREGATE FUZZY COGNITIVE MAPS**

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1 REAL-WORLD CASE STUDY

We apply the union, majority, and intersection to a real-world case study. Halbrendt et al. (2014) created four aggregate Fuzzy Cognitive Maps (FCMs) to compare the perspective of three rural communities in the central mid-hill region of Nepal with the views of researchers on the impact of conservation agriculture techniques on farming yield. Aggregating the three village FCMs and comparing the aggregate model with the researchers' FCM may provide additional insight into the differing views of villagers and researchers. Thus, we aggregate the three village FCMs using the union, majority, and intersection rules to illustrate how the aggregation procedures function and generate different aggregate maps. Fig. 4 (b)-(d) in Halbrendt et al. 2014 depict the three village FCMs. Edge weights are omitted from their visualizations for simplicity and are unavailable; however, this does not diminish the application of the three methods to them, as the approaches focus on what edges to include instead of determining the edge weights. Table 1 depicts the adjacency matrix of the graphs and indicates what FCM each edge was in. Figure 1 depicts the union aggregate map, Figure 2 displays the majority aggregate map, and Figure 3 illustrates the intersection aggregate map.

We compute the number of edges in each aggregate map, the density (the ratio between the edges present and the maximum number of possible edges), whether it contains feedback loops (i.e., cycles), and the top three nodes by degree (number of incoming and outgoing edges), in-degree (number of incoming edges), and out-degree (number of outgoing edges) centrality (Table 2). The intersection rule has the fewest edges and lowest density. A lower density value is often desired, as it indicates participants were selective in including edges. We observe the most important nodes according to centralities are similar over the three aggregation rules, although the majority and intersection rules elevate the importance of improved soil nutrients according to out-degree. Additionally, the intersection rule places maize and vegetable production as the two most important concepts according to in-degree, whereas maize production is not among the three most important concepts by in-degree centrality for the union rule. We hypothesize the similarities are likely due to only three input graphs being aggregated and that if more input graphs were used (e.g., the 31 input graphs for the Thumka village, which is shown in Figure 4(b) in Halbrendt et al. 2014), the differences in important concepts and densities would be greater. Finally, the analysis and comparison of the three aggregate FCMs produced by the union, majority, and intersection rule encompass a subset of the ways to analyze and compare FCMs, which is the subject of research papers (Engome Tchupo and Macht 2022).

Table 1: The adjacency matrix of the three input models from Halbrendt et al. (2014). The letter of the FCMs/subfigures the edge appears in is given in each cell (e.g., b means the edge was in the Thumka village FCM, depicted in Figure 4(b) in Halbrendt et al. 2014). The cell is labeled All if the edge was in all three FCMs, and empty cells mean the edge was not in any of the three village FCMs. Edges go from row to column (e.g., all three FCMs have an edge from increased market price to maize production).

	Increased Market Price	Higher Cost of Inputs	Increased Seed Cost	Decreased Household Income	Increased Household Size	Decreased Labor Availability	Stronger Social Pressures / Cultural / Religious Beliefs	Poor Soil Quality	Maize Production	Rice Production	Legume Production	Vegetable Production	Millet Production	Increased Market Sales	Improved Yield	Increased Soil Moisture	Improved Soil Nutrients	Greater Household Consumption	Improved Food Security	Increased Use of Cover Crop	Increased Use of Tillage
Increased Market Price									All	b, d	All	All	d								
Higher Cost of Inputs												c									
Increased Seed Cost												c									
Decreased Household Income																					
Increased Household Size									All	All	All	All	d								
Decreased Labor Availability									All	d	c, d	c, d	c								
Stronger Social Pressures / Cultural / Religious Beliefs										b, c	c, d	All									
Poor Soil Quality									All	All	d	All									
Maize Production																c	b, c				
Rice Production																	b				
Legume Production																	All				
Vegetable Production																					
Millet Production																c	b, c				
Increased Market Sales					All														All		
Improved Yield	All																		All		
Increased Soil Moisture								All	All	All	All	All	d		All						All
Improved Soil Nutrients									All	All	All	All	All			All					All
Greater Household Consumption																				b, d	
Improved Food Security																					
Increased Use of Cover Crop								All								All	All				
Increased Use of Tillage								d							c, d		d				

Figure 1: Union Aggregate FCM

REFERENCES

- Engome Tchupo, D., and G. A. Macht. 2022. "Comparing fuzzy cognitive maps: Methods and their applications in team communication". *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics* 92:103344.
- Halbrendt, J., S. A. Gray, S. Crow, T. Radovich, A. H. Kimura, and B. B. Tamang. 2014. "Differences in farmer and expert beliefs and the perceived impacts of conservation agriculture". *Global Environmental Change* 28:50–62.

Figure 2: Majority Aggregate FCM

Table 2: Computed network metrics for the three output FCMs.

	Number of Edges	Density	Feedback Loops	Top 3 Nodes By Degree Centrality	Top 3 Nodes By In-Degree Centrality	Top 3 Nodes By Out-Degree Centrality
Union	56	0.133	Y	1: Improved Soil Nutrients 2: Increased Soil Moisture 3: Vegetable Production	1: Vegetable Production 2: Rice Production 2: Legume Production	1: Increased Soil Moisture 2: Improved Soil Nutrients 3: Increased Market Price 3: Increased Household Size 3: Decreased Labor Availability
Majority	43	0.102	Y	1: Improved Soil Nutrients 2: Increased Soil Moisture 3: Maize Production 3: Legume Production 3: Vegetable Production	1: Vegetable Production 2: Maize Production 2: Rice Production 2: Legume Production	1: Increased Soil Moisture 1: Improved Soil Nutrients 2: Increased Market Price 2: Increased Household Size
Intersection	34	0.081	Y	1: Increased Soil Moisture 1: Improved Soil Nutrients 2: Maize Production 2: Vegetable Production	1: Maize Production 1: Vegetable Production 2: Rice Production 2: Legume Production	1: Increased Soil Moisture 1: Improved Soil Nutrients 2: Increased Household Size

Figure 3: Intersection Aggregate FCM